

Subalternity: A Comparative Study on Toni Morrison's the Bluest Eye and Arundhati Roy's The God of Small Things

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Abstract

This paper extracts the theme of subalternity found in two marginalized groups located in United States and India. The hegemony of discrimination, humiliation and inequality differ from place to place but the outcomes of such issues are common to all folks. This underlining concept is dealt through this study. Both writers are beautifully and effectively shown the plight of women in USA and Indian society. The writers have taken up the issues of subaltern to fight for their identity and economic and social freedom. This paper indicates the truth of people is marginalized from the country. The subaltern study clearly demonstrates the sufferings of racism, colour discrimination, gender and searching their identity.

Keywords: Relationship, Culture, Indifferent and Patriarchal

Comparative Literature- A Short Introduction

The discipline of Comparative Literature is a method in the study of literature in at least two ways. First, Comparative Literature means the knowledge of more than one national language and literature, and/or it means the knowledge and application of other disciplines in and for the study of literature and second, Comparative Literature has an ideology of inclusion of the Other, be that a marginal literature in its several meanings of marginality, a genre, various text types, etc. At the same time, however, the discipline paid more attention to 'Other' literatures than any of the national literatures. Comparative Literature has intrinsically a content and form which facilitate the cross-cultural and interdisciplinary study of literature and it has a history that substantiated this content and form. On the whole comparative literature seems to be an outcome of intellectual challenge and wide range of cross-cultural knowledge.

About the Author-Toni Morrison

Toni Morrison (February 18, 1931) is an American novelist, essayist, editor, teacher, and professor emeritus at Princeton University. Morrison is a winner of Pulitzer Prize and the American Book Award in the year 1988 for her phenomenal work *Beloved*. The

novel has been adapted to a filmic version. Morrison was awarded the Nobel Prize in Literature in 1993. On May 29, 2012, President Barack Obama presented Morrison with the Presidential Medal of Freedom. In 2016, she received the PEN/Saul Bellow Award for Achievement in American Fiction.

About the Author-Arundhati Roy

Arundhati Roy who is a recipient of Booker Prize award was born on November 24, 1961 in Shillong, Meghalaya, India. Her full name is Suzanna Arundhati Roy. She basically comes from an activist family, her mother Mary Roy, was a well-known social activist from Kerala. She spent her crucial childhood years in Ayamanam a small town near Kotlayam. Roy met her second husband, who is a filmmaker Pradip Krishen, in 1984, and Roy herself played a village girl in his award-winning movie 'Massey Sahib'. Roy is a cousin of prominent media personality Prannoy Roy, the head of the Leading Indian TV media group NDTV. She lives in New Delhi.

The Comparative Study

The present paper has been attempted to explore the elements of Subaltern and Feminism in Toni Morrison's *The Bluest Eye* and Arundhati Roy's *The God of Small Things*. The paper throws light on some important elements of life that how the emotion of love is associated with sadness, how an individual's childhood experiences affect his/her perspectives and entire life. Beyond the emotional aspects it also presents the constant struggle of women against their exploitation, torture and struggle which they undergo because of the male dominated and conservative society.

The main examination of this paper is the comparison of two marginalized groups; African American in the United States and Dalits in India. The two societies USA and India are compared on the basis of socio economic status, cultural behavior, and political structures. The definition of the subaltern identity is represented with respect to two different societies with the study of women. Violence is not always external, the root cause starts from the internal surroundings. There is a form of domestic violence which subjugates and exploits women. This leads to the chaos in familial structures, traumatic effect on children and totally it confuses the entire relationship within the members of the family. Both the African American and the Dalits fight for their national identity guaranteed by their constitution. Literature paves way to these sufferings and struggles by scripting the true stories. Additionally comparative literature gives a wider scope for the universe to understand the study better with a dual analysis. Literature gives voice to these subalterns who are silenced.

Subaltern Aspects in Morrison's *The Bluest Eye*

The subaltern theme found in *The Bluest Eye* is evident even in real life in America. Particularly in the post-modern analysis, the voices against this racial segregation are more prominent. Literature gave and gives voices to those who really searching for identity based on the colour issues. And it was Toni Morrison who checked the pulse of everyone through her writings. Pecola, in *The Bluest Eye* desires to have white skin, blue eyes inspite of naturally being dark in complexion. This thought of Pecola to change her natural to completely unnatural is the outburst of racial discrimination held at American society.

Racial discrimination is grown in such a way that even trauma level of the people is still occupied with the thoughts of racial difference. Toni Morrison has taken her pen as an important weapon to inform the world that black identity is not inferior in any way. Black people are caught between two grotesque worlds, the one which already banished them and the other world which is not ready to accept them. Under such circumstances, black people were suffering from the acceptance of alien

culture. The so called white society treats them as strictly suitable for physical labour and hard work. The white society framed in such a way that they felt the white race to be superior and black complexion to be inferior. As said earlier, Pecola earns her desire to have white skin, blonde hair and blue skin.

Each night, without fail, she prayed for blue eyes. Fervently, for a year she had prayed. Although somewhat discouraged, she was not without hope. To have something as wonderful as that happen would take a long, long time. (The Bluest Eye 35)

Subaltern Aspects in Roy's The God of Small Things

In Arundhati Roy's *The God of Small Things*, Ammu and Velutha are the tragic representatives of subaltern identity. Velutha was Ammu's childhood friend, it happened that when she returned to her hometown, she met Velutha and renewed her friendship with him. When Ammu was all alone in the house she found an emotional companion with Velutha. Ammu felt that Velutha brings some consolation to her life. Meanwhile her love towards him grew boundless. This unconditional love led to illicit relationship between Ammu and Velutha. But this was strictly opposed by Velutha's father as he did not like Ammu for she was a divorcee. Velutha's father took this relationship to the next level by informing this to Mammachi what he had witnessed. There ends the relationship between Ammu and Velutha; Ammu was locked up in her room and Velutha was arrested by the police and beaten up till his death. Ammu too ended her life pathetically by committing suicide. The two subalterns discussed in *The God of Small Things*, met the tragic end of their life. Both were never given an opportunity to open their mouth and speak for themselves. They were under a force to actually admit under pressure and not of true to their knowledge. Velutha was brutally killed, whereas Ammu was overwhelmed with pressure and the only way to escape from this consequence is to commit suicide. The thorough examination of caste and gender is seen from the two victims Ammu and Velutha. The effects of caste, gender, untouchable towards the downtrodden are clearly manifested through Arundhati Roy's *The God of Small Things*.

Conclusion

Analysing both the works of art, it is scrutinized that the two different nations USA and India are having a group of people who face this global issues of gender, race and colour. Both the subalterns possess the historical, political, economic, cultural root cause for their positions in the society. The brutal deed of slavery, racism in United States is equalled with the caste and gender problems in India. Though the socio-cultural structure of both the countries differ from each other, the resulting effect of discrimination, humiliation, unequal treatment, subordinate state of mind give the same result in both the nations. The scholarly treatment of such issues should be taken wider and reduce such effects caused on people with blood and shed.

Note: This paper has adhered to VIII Edition of MLA Handbook for Writers of Research Papers.

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